

Photosynthetically Active Radiation Temperature Dependent Models and Its Variability with Climatic Variables over Akure, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) is an essential input for applications pertaining to biomass production, plant physiology, and natural lighting in greenhouses. It is the amount of light energy necessary for photosynthesis to occur, and the wavelengths of this light are typically between 400 and 700 nm. In this study, the photosynthetically active radiation for Akure (latitude 7.28°N, longitude 5.30°E, and 375 m asl.), located in the coastal region of Nigeria, was estimated and investigated using data on the monthly averaged daily global solar radiation, relative humidity, wind speed, minimum and maximum temperature from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) archives over a thirty-eight-year period (1984–2021). In order to determine the accuracy of the

models, eight (8) new temperature PAR-based models were developed for the location and statistical tests were conducted using the coefficient of determination (R^2), mean bias error (MBE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean percentage error (MPE), t-test, and index of agreement (IA). The findings demonstrated that PAR for Akure is lowest in the month of August with $6.5320 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$ during the rainy season (April to October) and highest during the dry season (November to March), with $8.6670 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$ in March. The best model equation for calculating PAR for Akure was found to be the one that links the PAR and natural logarithm of temperature changes; its R^2 , MBE, RMSE, MPE, t-test, and

IA values were 68.1%, 0.0032 MJm⁻²day⁻¹, 0.5208 MJm⁻²day⁻¹, -0.4479%, 0.0204, and 82.8013%, respectively.

Keywords: *Akure, Models, NASA, PAR, Statistical indicators.*

Introduction

The primary force behind the climate on Earth and, by extension, the majority of living organisms is solar radiation (Trenberth *et al.*, 2009; Stocker *et al.*, 2013). The so-called photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) range, which is equivalent to solar radiation in the spectral interval between 400 and 700 nm (McCree, 1972), provides around half of the energy from the Sun (Yu *et al.*, 2015). This definition relates to how important solar radiation is for plant photosynthesis and related processes like biomass production and greenhouse gas emissions from crops at this spectral interval (Keane *et al.*, 2017; Manevski *et al.*, 2017; Tan *et al.*, 2018; Roebroek *et al.*, 2020). The 400–700 nm range of the solar radiation spectrum that photoautotrophic organisms, such as plants, algae, and cyanobacteria, require for photosynthesis is known as photosynthetically active radiation, or PAR. Playing a major role in the cycle of water and carbon, PAR is a crucial element in modelling Earth systems and global ecosystems. PAR regulates photosynthesis and, by extension, biomass productivity overall, in conjunction with air temperature, water availability, and atmospheric CO₂ concentration (Thomas *et al.*, 2023). The range of solar radiation that organisms use for photosynthesis is known as photosynthetically active radiation, or PAR. Since solar radiation is a major factor in plant photosynthesis, measuring PAR is vital. PAR rises in response to an increase in leaf photosynthesis (Mercado *et al.*, 2009).

According to the chemical equation, plants that are employed to synthesise food can be shown to exhibit this radiation component (PAR) (Akpootu *et al.*, 2019a).

where the photon (PAR) represents light energy wavelength range (0.4-0.7 μm) that is best suitable for photosynthesis to occur.

Because it is the solar energy source for vegetative photosynthesis, which provides us with products like food and fibre sources, carriers of biofuel, and additional material sources that support industrial processes, this component of the solar radiation spectrum (PAR) is critically needed. It is the primary determinant in the rate at which solar energy is converted into biologically mediated energy and plays a major role in plant growth. For many applications, including studies of radiation climate, vegetation remote sensing, photosynthesis and canopy radiation regimes, a critical input in models estimating plant productivity, and carbon exchange between ecosystem and atmosphere, accurate prediction and perception of this radiometric parameter, PAR, are essential. Within the 400–700 nm light wavelength range, Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) can be measured using a silicon photovoltaic detector. Most PAR sensors can detect the photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) of photosynthetically active light, which can also be used to quantify PAR (Udo and Aro, 1999; Jacovides *et al.*, 2004; Escobedo *et al.*, 2009).

A few numbers of studies have been conducted to examine photosynthetically active radiation for various places. One such study was conducted by Nwokolo *et al.* (2017), who examined modelling and estimation of photosynthetically active radiation throughout several climatic zones in Nigeria. Empirical models for estimating photosynthetically active

radiation over Akure, South Western, Nigeria, were established by Akpootu *et al.* (2019a) in another work. Nwokolo *et al.* (2022) used hybrid machine learning with physics-based models to explore the effects of climate change and Mateo - solar factors on photosynthetically active radiation projection. Nwokolo *et al.* (2023) evaluated the impacts of urbanisation and climate change on photosynthetically active radiation using machine learning and physics-based hybridization models. A study on the assessment and analysis of photosynthetically active radiation over Benin, Nigeria, was carried out by Akpootu *et al.* (2023a). Using meteorological factors, Akpootu *et al.* (2023b) conducted a study on the estimation and investigation of photosynthetically active radiation over Ikeja, Nigeria. To name a few further studies, there are Sunday *et al.* (2016), Etuk *et al.* (2016), Nwokolo *et al.* (2018), and Thomas *et al.* (2023).

The purpose of this work is to develop new temperature PAR based models that can estimate PAR for Akure, which is located in the coastal region of Nigeria, as well as to examine the variability of photosynthetically active radiation with other meteorological parameters.

Methodology

The National Aeronautic and Space Administration (NASA) archives provided the measured monthly average daily global solar radiation, relative humidity, wind speed, maximum and minimum temperatures for Akure, Nigeria during a thirty-eight-year period (1984 - 2021). The following formula was used to compute the average monthly extraterrestrial radiation on a horizontal surface (H_0) in MJ/m²/day for days. This allowed for the calculation of the monthly average (Iqbal, 1983; Zekai, 2008; Akpootu and Abdullahi, 2022).

$$H_0 \left(\frac{24}{\pi} \right) I_{sc} \left[10.033 \cos \left(\frac{360n}{360} \right) \right] \left[\cos \varphi \cos \delta \sin \omega_s + \left(\frac{2\pi \omega_s}{360} \right) \sin \varphi \sin \delta \right] \quad (2)$$

where I_{sc} is the solar constant ($=1367 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$), φ is the latitude of the site, δ is the solar declination and ω_s is the mean sunrise hour angle for the given month and n is the number of days of the year starting from 1st January to 31st of December. The solar declination, δ and the mean sunrise hour angle, ω_s can be calculated using the following equation (Iqbal, 1983; Zekai, 2008; Akpootu *et al.*, 2023c)

$$\delta = 23.45 \sin \left\{ 360 \left(\frac{284+n}{365} \right) \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$\omega_s = \cos^{-1}(-\tan \varphi \tan \delta) \quad (4)$$

For a given month, the maximum possible sunshine duration (monthly average day length (S_0)) was computed (Iqbal, 1983; Zekai, 2008) by

$$S_0 = \frac{2}{15} \omega_s \quad (5)$$

Since, there is no standard weather station that routinely measure PAR in Nigeria and in particular Akure. Therefore, PAR was obtained using the formula (Howell *et al.*, 1983; Li *et al.*, 2010).

$$PAR = 0.45 H_{mea} \quad (6)$$

where H_{mea} is the measured global solar radiation in MJm⁻²day⁻¹.

According to Monteith's generalisation (1990), the alien PAR₀ was calculated to be 40% of the extraterrestrial global solar radiation. Because the ratio of the earth's distance from the sun on any given day to the mean distance over the course of the year is never greater than 3.5% away from one, it was supposed that the sun-earth distance did not vary seasonally (Gate, 1980). The expression was used to determine the extraterrestrial photosynthetically active

radiation, or PAR_0 (Nwokolo, 2017; Akpootu *et al.*, 2019a).

$$PAR_0 = 0.40 H_0 \quad (7)$$

The PAR and PAR_0 are in MJ/m²/day.

The Mean temperature (T_{mean}) was obtained using equation (8) as given by Akpootu *et al.* (2019b); Akpootu *et al.* (2022a).

$$T_{mean} = \frac{T_{max} + T_{min}}{2} \quad (8)$$

The temperature ratio (T_r) was obtained using Akpootu and Sanusi (2015) as

$$T_r = \frac{T_{max}}{T_{min}} \quad (9)$$

The accuracy of the developed models was statistically tested by calculating the Mean Bias Error (MBE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Percentage Error (MPE), t-test, Index of Agreement (IA) and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The MBE, RMSE and MPE was calculated using the equation (El-Sabaii and Trabea; 2005; Akpootu *et al.*, 2019c,d,e,f; Akpootu *et al.*, 2022b; Olomiyesan *et al.*, 2021).

$$MBE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (PAR_{i,cal} - PAR_{i,mea}) \quad (10)$$

$$RMSE = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (PAR_{i,cal} - PAR_{i,mea})^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (11)$$

$$MPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{PAR_{i,mea} - PAR_{i,cal}}{PAR_{i,mea}} \right) * 100 \quad (12)$$

Among the tests for mean value is the t-test, as defined by student Bevington (1969); the random variable t, with $n - 1$ degrees of freedom, can be provided by the relation as

$$t = \left[\frac{(n-1)(MBE)^2}{(RMSE)^2 - (MBE)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (13)$$

The index of agreement (IA) was calculated using the equation as given in (14) as reported in Akpootu *et al.* (2022b).

$$IA = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (PAR_{i,cal} - PAR_{i,mea})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (|PAR_{i,cal} - \overline{PAR}_{i,mea}| + |PAR_{i,mea} - \overline{PAR}_{i,mea}|)^2} \quad (14)$$

From the above equation (10) – (14), the $PAR_{i,mea}$, $PAR_{i,cal}$ and n are referred to as the i^{th} measured, i^{th} calculated values of daily photosynthetically active radiation and the total number of observations respectively. According to Iqbal (1983) and Chen *et al.* (2004), a low RMSE is preferred and a zero value for MBE is the most appropriate. Furthermore, the model performs better the smaller the values of the MBE, RMSE, and MPE. The average degree of overestimation in the computed values is indicated by positive MPE and MBE values, whilst underestimating is indicated by negative values. A low MPE value is preferred for improved model performance, and a percentage error of between -10% and +10% is regarded as acceptable (Merges *et al.*, 2006). The smaller the value, the better the performance. MBE and RMSE are in MJm⁻²day⁻¹, MPE and IA are in %, and the t-test is non-dimensional (Akpootu *et al.*, 2023c). For better data modelling, the coefficient of determination R^2 should approach 1 (100%) as closely as possible (Akpootu and Ilyasu, 2015a; Akpootu and Ilyasu, 2015b).

The proposed temperature PAR based models developed in this study are of the form:

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = a + b \ln \Delta T \quad (15a)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = a + b \Delta T^{0.5} \quad (15b)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = a + b \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) \quad (15c)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = a + b \Delta T^{0.5} + c \exp(\Delta T^{0.5}) \quad (15d)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = a + b \Delta T + c(\Delta T)^2 + d \ln \Delta T \quad (15e)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = a + b \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) + c \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right)^2 + d \exp\left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) \quad (15f)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = a + b \Delta T + c T_{mean} + d Tr \quad (15g)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = a + b \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) + c \ln \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) \quad (15h)$$

where PAR, PAR_0 and S_0 are as previously defined. ΔT Is the difference between the monthly average daily maximum and minimum temperature i.e., $T_{max} - T_{min}$ and the constants a , b and c are empirical coefficients determined by regression analysis and the other terms are the model correlation parameters.

Results and Discussion

PAR Regression Analysis

Based on equations 15a–15h, the examined temperature-based models with corresponding PAR empirical coefficients were developed in this work for Akure. They are as follows:

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = 0.028 + 0.215 \ln \Delta T \quad (16a)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = 0.147 + 0.119 \Delta T^{0.5} \quad (16b)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = 0.374 + 0.181 \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) \quad (16c)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = -0.772 + 0.483 \Delta T^{0.5} - 0.00966 \exp(\Delta T^{0.5}) \quad (16d)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = -10.4 - 1.43 \Delta T + 0.0257 (\Delta T)^2 + 9.83 \ln \Delta T \quad (16e)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = -4.60 + 2.22 \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) - 5.04 \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right)^2 + 2.95 \exp\left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) \quad (16f)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = 0.11 + 0.0143 \Delta T + 0.0089 T_{mean} + 0.029 Tr \quad (16g)$$

$$\frac{PAR}{PAR_0} = 1.49 - 0.889 \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) + 1.15 \ln \left(\frac{\Delta T}{S_0}\right) \quad (16h)$$

Table 1a. Validation of the PAR Temperature Based Models for Akure Under Different Statistical Test

Models	R ²	MBE	RMSE	MPE	t	IA
Eqn16a	68.1	0.0032	0.5208	-0.4479	0.0204	82.8013
Eqn16b	65.6	0.0088	0.5402	-0.5512	0.0538	80.9154
Eqn16c	64.1	0.0057	0.5536	-0.5497	0.0340	78.9768
Eqn16d	78.1	0.0093	0.4377	-0.3424	0.0706	89.7036

Eqn16e	88.1	-0.6492	0.7158	8.1838	7.1419	81.2282
Eqn16f	84.2	-0.1349	0.3938	1.5487	1.2096	92.1767
Eqn16g	65.1	-0.0303	0.5385	0.0031	0.18670	82.9086
Eqn16h	80.4	0.0772	0.4249	-1.1703	0.6130	90.6217

Table 1b. Ranking of the Evaluated PAR Temperature Based Models for Akure Based on the Statistical Test

Models	R ²	MBE	RMSE	MPE	t	IA	Total
Eqn16a	5	1	4	3	1	5	19
Eqn16b	6	3	6	5	3	7	30
Eqn16c	8	2	7	4	2	8	31
Eqn16d	4	4	3	2	4	3	20
Eqn16e	1	8	8	8	8	6	39
Eqn16f	2	7	1	7	7	1	25
Eqn16g	7	5	5	1	5	4	27
Eqn16h	3	6	2	6	6	2	25

The several statistical tests employed in this investigation are displayed in Table 1a. It suggests that equation 16e is the best model and has the greatest value (88.1%) based on the R² of the model. Equation 16a, which is deemed the best model based on the MBE, has the least value with an overestimation of 0.0032 MJm⁻²day⁻¹ in the estimated value. Equation 16f, the best model, has the lowest root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.3838 MJm⁻²day⁻¹. According to the MPE, all of the models fall within the allowed range (MPE ±10%), with equation 16g being the best model and having the lowest value with an overestimation of 0.0031% in the estimated value. On the t – test, the model equation 16a has the least value with 0.0204

which was judged the best model. However, Based on the IA the model, equation 16f has the highest value with 92.1767 % and is the best model.

Table 1b displays the models' ranking, which was determined by validating the models in Table 1a. The various models yielded total ranks ranging from 19 to 39. Because model equation 16a has the lowest ranking value and is therefore most appropriate for predicting PAR for Akure, it was noticed that based on the overall results, this model is the best and most sensitive.

The result of model 16a and 16b were compared with that of the results of model 17a and 17b reported by Akpootu *et al.* (2019a) as they present the same model formulation.

Table 1c. Comparison of Evaluated Photosynthetically Active Radiation for Akure Based on Model 16a

Statistical indicators	In this work	Akpootu et al. (2019a)
R ² (%)	68.1 (2)	74.2 (1)
MBE(MJm ⁻² day ⁻¹)	0.0032(1)	0.0111 (2)
RMSE (MJm ⁻² day ⁻¹)	0.5208 (1)	0.5837 (2)
MPE (%)	-0.4479 (1)	-0.7278 (2)
t – test	0.0204 (1)	0.0631 (2)
IA (%)	82.8013(2)	99.8650 (1)

The model in this study performed better as compared with that of Akpootu *et al.* (2019a) through ranking, since the rank acquired in this study is 8 while that of Akpootu *et al.* (2019a) is

10. This result could be attributed to the fact that this study utilized 38 years data, while that of Akpootu *et al.* (2019a) uses 31 years data.

Table 1d. Comparison of Evaluated Photosynthetically Active Radiation for Akure Based on Model 16b

Statistical indicators	In this work	Akpootu et al. (2019a)
R ² (%)	65.6(2)	70.6(1)
MBE(MJm ⁻² day ⁻¹)	0.0088(1)	-0.0178(2)
RMSE (MJm ⁻² day ⁻¹)	0.5402(1)	0.6260(2)
MPE (%)	-0.5512(2)	-0.4602(1)
t – test	0.0538(1)	0.0943(2)
IA (%)	80.9154(2)	99.8452(1)

This shows that the model in this study is in agreement with that of Akpootu *et al.* (2019a) as they have equal ranking of 9 in each. The result of this study reviewed that the models 16b and 17b are in perfect agreement with that reported by Akpootu *et al.* (2019a) indicating that either of the models can be used to estimate PAR in Akure based on the models formulation.

Variation of PAR with Climatic Variables for Akure

The monthly change of PAR for Akure over the research period (1984–2021) is depicted in Figure 1. According to the results, the month of August had the lowest PAR value, measuring 6.5320 MJm⁻²day⁻¹, while the month of March had the highest PAR value, measuring 8.6670 MJm⁻²day⁻¹. The outcome also shows that the largest PAR value happened during the dry season, while the lowest PAR values occur during the rainy season. Nevertheless, February, April, and November have values of 8.5783 MJm⁻²day⁻¹, 8.6205 MJm⁻²day⁻¹, and 8.5442 MJm⁻²day⁻¹, respectively, which are significantly closer to the maximum value. The value of PAR occurs in the rainy season in April, which is when the decline starts, but the values in February and November occur during the dry season.

A comparison of the calculated and measured photosynthetically active radiation temperature-based models for Akure is presented in Figure 2. Equation 16e's model, which had a minimum value of 6.2286 MJm⁻²day⁻¹ in July, clearly underestimated the measured PAR and other estimated temperature-based models in the months of January to March and May to October, including December. This is evident from the figure. In the rainy season (May to

June) and the partially dry season (October to November), the measured PAR overestimated the estimated temperature based models. With a peak value of 9.3942 MJm⁻²day⁻¹ in March, which fell during the dry season, the model, equation 16h, overstated the measured PAR and other estimated temperature based models in the months of March through April. Nevertheless, in the months of January and July through September, the model, equation 16c, overestimated the measured PAR and other estimated temperature-based models. In the month of February, the model, equation 16g, somewhat overestimates the observed PAR and other estimated temperature-based models; in the month of November, it underestimates both the measured and the estimated temperature-based models.

For the Akure study period, Figure 3 displays the monthly change of PAR with relative humidity. It showed that the relative humidity increases from January to its peak value of 90.0134 % in July and then slightly decreases to August and maintains almost similar value to September, and then gradually decreases down to December, while the PAR increases from January to its maximum value of 8.6670 MJm⁻²day⁻¹ in March and then decreases to its least value of 6.5320 MJm⁻²day⁻¹ in August. From August through November, the PAR rises even more before declining until December.

The monthly variation of PAR with wind speed for Akure during the study period is depicted in Figure 4, which makes it evident that while the wind speed increases from January to April and then decreases to May, the PAR increases from January to its highest value of 8.6670 MJm⁻²day⁻¹

in March and then decreases to its lowest value of $6.5320 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$ in August. Meanwhile, the wind speed increases from May to its maximum value of 2.6642 ms^{-1} in August and decreases to its minimum value of 1.6279 ms^{-1} in November, and then rises to December. The figure indicated

that the highest value of wind speed and the lowest value of PAR were found in the month of August, indicating that wind speed might decrease the value of atmospheric PAR. The PAR further increases from August to November and then declines to December.

Figure 1. Monthly Variation of PAR for Akure

Figure 2. Comparison between the Measured and Estimated Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) Temperature Based Models for Akure

Figure 3. Monthly Variation of PAR with Relative Humidity during the Period of Thirty-Eight Years (1984 – 2021) for Akure

Figure 4. Monthly Variation of PAR with Wind Speed during the Period of Thirty-Eight Years (1984 – 2021) for Akure

The monthly change of PAR with Akure's mean temperature over the course of the investigation is shown in Figure 5. The PAR rises from January to its highest point of $8.6670 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$ in March and subsequently falls to its lowest point of $6.5320 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$ in August, based on the data. In addition, the average temperature rises from January to its greatest point of 27.2951°C in March before falling until August. The mean temperature rises from August to October before falling to its lowest value of 23.2296°C in December, in line with the PAR's increase from August to November and subsequent reduction to December.

The monthly variation of PAR with global solar radiation for Akure during the investigation period is displayed in Figure 6. It appears from

Figure 5. Monthly Variation of PAR with Mean Temperature during the Period of Thirty-Eight Years (1984 – 2021) for Akure

Conclusion

Since photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) is essential to plant growth and development, it is a significant input parameter for determining plant productivity. In this work, the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) for Akure, a Coastal region in Nigeria (latitude 7.28°N , longitude 5.30°E , and elevation 375 m

the figure that there is a direct correlation between the PAR and global solar radiation, as the PAR varies similarly with the latter. As the PAR rises from January to its maximum value of $8.6670 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$ in March and falls to its lowest value of $6.5320 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$ in August. It is evident, comparably, from January to March, when it reaches its highest value of $19.2600 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$, and from August, when it falls to its lowest value of $14.5156 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$, the global solar radiation increases. On the other hand, the global solar radiation also rises from August to November and then falls to December, just as the PAR does from August to November and then to December. Thus, the outcome showed a direct correlation between the PAR and solar radiation.

Figure 6. Monthly Variation of PAR with Global Solar Radiation during the Period of Thirty-Eight Years (1984 – 2021) for Akure

above sea level), is estimated and investigated. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) archives provided the data used in this investigation. This study made use of monthly average daily global solar radiation, relative humidity, wind speed, minimum and maximum temperatures over a thirty-eight-year period (1984–2021). Eight (8)

new temperature PAR-based models were developed for this study, and they were compared using the following statistical measures: t-test, index of agreement (IA), mean bias error (MBE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean percentage error (MPE), and coefficient of determination (R^2). Results indicated that in the dry season, in March, photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) for Akure was greater at $8.6670 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$, while in the rainy season, in August, it was lower at $6.5320 \text{ MJm}^{-2}\text{day}^{-1}$. Model equation 16a represents the optimal model for Akure, based on the newly constructed temperature PAR-based models.

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